

**RDA Minimal Metadata for Learning Resources *Formal Education* Examples
October 2021**

	A	B	C	D	E	F
1	Formal education					
2	Name	Definition	Type	Allowed values	Example	Other constraints
3	Title	The human readable name of the resource.	TEXT (1000)	Free text	ENVRI Community International Winter School on data FAIRness	
4	Abstract / Description	A brief synopsis about or description of the learning resource.	TEXT (2000)	Free text	The 2021 ENVRI Community International Winter School, centred on the FAIR principles of data management, has covered semantic navigation, Jupyter environments for visualisation and data discovery, resource access tools and cloud computing. In recognition of the difficulties of distance learning, the organisers structured 40 hours of presence (including preparations) over a two-week period, with scheduled lectures and presentations in the mornings (09-11), followed by associated group and individual work time (11-12).	
5	Author(s)	Name of entity(ies) authoring the resource.	TEXT	Multiple authors should be listed with commas between the names. Names should include given or first name and family or surname, and a personal identifier such as an ORCID, if available.	LifeWatch ERIC Training Team	
6	Primary Language	Language in which the resource was originally published or made available.	TEXT (2)	String composed by a code as defined by the code set ISO 639-1:2002	en	
7	Keyword(s)	Keywords or tags used to describe the resource.	TEXT (100)	Free text or keywords from a given vocabulary	ENVRI-FAIR FAIRNESS Cloud Computing VRE Jupyter Data Semantics Metadata	repeatable singular value

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8	License	A license document that applies to this content, typically indicated by URL	TEXT (100); should be available for URL as well; specify in application profile	Free text or keywords from a given vocabulary, e.g., the NERC Vocabulary Server (NVS), http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L08/current/	CC BY 4.0	
9	Version Date	Version date for the most recently published or broadcast resource.	DATE	Format: YYYY-MM-DD IETF RFC3339 ISO 8601	2021-01-22	
10	URL to Resource	URL that resolves to the learning resource or to a "landing page" for the resource that contains important contextual information including the direct resolvable link to the resource, if applicable. Should be a PID, if possible.	TEXT (1000)	Free text	https://training.envri.eu/course/view.php?id=52	
11	Resource URL Type	Controlled vocabulary designating the persistent identifier schemes used for the resource, e.g., DOI, ARK, Handle.	TEXT (1000)	Codelist from a CV including values like URL, ARK, DOI, etc.	URL	
12	Target Group (Audience) (row 32)	Principle users(s) for which the resource was designed.	TEXT (40)	Codelist from a recommended CV	Data centre staff Researchers PhD candidates	repeatable

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13	Learning Resource Type (row 31)	The predominant type or kind that characterizes the learning resource.	TEXT (40)	<p>Codelist from a CV including values like:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - exercise - simulation - questionnaire - diagram - figure - graph - index - slide - table - narrative text - exam - experiment - problem statement - self assessment - lecture 	Lecture	
14	Learning Outcome(s) (See RDA_row 46)	Descriptions of what knowledge, skills or abilities students should acquire on completion of the resource.	TEXT (1000)	Free text	<p>With this course the learners will be able to know the state of the art technologies relevant to FAIRification of services based on real-life use cases. This will encourage the adoption of new technology to enhance data center functionality and will enable new knowledge-exchange networks for ENVRI data professionals.</p>	

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15	Access Cost; see RDA_row5	Access cost: Choice stating whether or not there is a fee for use of the resource (CV = Y/N/Maybe with recommendation that further explanation of "Maybe" goes in the Description field for "It depends" or "It changes" explanations).	TEXT (8)	Codelist with values like Yes, No, Maybe OR Codelist associated with a CV with values like open access; embargoed access; restricted access; metadata only access	Open access	
16	Expertise Level (Skill level; see RDA_row 34)	Target skill level in the topic being taught; example values include: beginner, intermediate, advanced.	TEXT	Codelist with values like beginner, intermediate, advanced	Intermediate	
17						
18						